

GLOSSALGIA - PREVENTION AND TREATMENT

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Glossalgia is a disease that consists in the appearance of pain and a burning sensation of the tongue in the absence of obvious causes and other clinical manifestations on the mucous membranes. Sometimes similar symptoms spread to the lips, palate, or the entire oral mucosa.

This disease is more likely to affect middle-aged and elderly women, in men it occurs several times less often. Unlike other diseases, with glossalgia there are no organic causes of pain. Despite the fact that patients often report the development of pain after injuries, the latter can only act as a triggering factor. The disease should be distinguished from glossitis - an inflammatory disease in which, in addition to pain and burning, external changes in the mucous membranes are observed: redness, ulceration, pronounced plaque, etc.

Reasons for glossalgia

Many patients with glossalgia associate the onset of a symptom with trauma to the tongue with sharp edges of fillings or teeth with chipped enamel, as well as improperly installed crowns and prostheses. More often the disease appears after disorders of the autonomic nervous system. As the disease progresses, it becomes chronic.[5.6] This is a functional disorder that has no organic causes. Researchers associate its appearance with diseases of the gastrointestinal tract. Most often there is a combination of disorders of the nervous system, vascular lesions and diseases of the digestive system. A stimulating factor can be diseases that lead to a decrease in tissue sensitivity or change the response to mechanical stimuli. Glossalgia can also develop against the background of the following diseases: ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke; encephalitis of any origin; neurosyphilis.

Aggravating factors can be hypovitaminosis, lack of iron, minerals, endocrine diseases, infections and autoimmune pathologies. Affects the disease and the intake of certain drugs - chemotherapy drugs, antihistamines, etc. Studies show that the disease may be one of the signs of visceroreflex bulbar syndrome, in which the vagus and glossopharyngeal nerves are affected. Violations of the transmission of nerve impulses cause glossalgia, as they lead to the appearance of false sensations. And external stimuli can only exacerbate the symptom, which explains the high incidence of the disease in people with prostheses and crowns.[1.4.6]

Manifestations of glossalgia

With this disease, patients note a burning sensation, tingling, itching, soreness in the tongue. An unpleasant symptom may appear from time to time or disturb constantly. Some patients associate these manifestations with the intake of spicy food. Indirect symptoms are dry mouth, fatigue during a conversation. It is worth noting that with overwork and nervous excitement, the symptoms become more pronounced. Sometimes the symptoms of glossalgia manifest themselves only in certain situations, for example, before an important event. During the meal, the manifestations of the disease may become less pronounced up to the complete absence. The feeling of burning and tingling often spreads to the lateral areas and the tip of the tongue. On the back and root of the tongue, they occur

much less frequently. The pain is widespread, there is no pronounced focus, and localization can change rapidly. The symptom may disappear and appear in another area. It is important to consider that there are no visible changes in the mucous membrane of the tongue and oral cavity. Only a part of people suffering from this disease may experience swelling or plaque in the tongue, hypertrophy of the lingual papillae. Varicose veins of the tongue are typical for elderly patients. Many people with glossalgia have symptoms of depression. Sometimes there is excitability, increased anxiety, suspiciousness. Many people suffer from the fear of developing cancer and other serious diseases, and the disease is accompanied by sleep disturbances, pain in the chest area, etc.[2.3]

Possible Complications

This disease does not threaten health, but significantly reduces the quality of life. If you ignore an unpleasant symptom, glossalgia can become chronic. Her symptoms will occur from time to time, exacerbating the unstable psycho-emotional state. Against the background of pain, anxiety, eating disorders, sleep disorders, nervousness, phobias can develop. As the condition worsens, not only the dentist should be treated, but also other specialists - a neurologist, psychiatrist or psychotherapist. A long-term symptom can cause forced dietary restrictions, which can affect the general state of health and cause beriberi, weight loss, lack of minerals. Possible complications include inflammatory diseases of the oral cavity. For example, a lack of saliva can lead to aphthous stomatitis, and when exposed to adverse factors or injuries, the likelihood of glossitis, gingivitis and other ailments increases.[5.6]

Features of diagnostics

It is important to distinguish glossalgia from organic diseases of the tongue that develop as a result of injuries, neuralgia and neuritis. Also, the doctor will make sure that there are no bite defects. The main diagnostic criterion of glossalgia is the inconsistency of sensations with the intensity of impact. In addition, visible changes in the tongue and mucous membranes are almost completely absent. With injuries, the pain has a clear localization, does not extend beyond the boundaries of the lesion. With neuralgia, sensations occur briefly, in the region of nerve innervation. With neuritis, pain most often appears only on one side, and is also accompanied by impaired sensitivity. Treatment Methods The treatment of glossalgia begins with the sanitation of the oral cavity: the doctor will prescribe the treatment of caries, the replacement of incorrectly installed prostheses, as well as the replacement of fillings that have expired. The manufacture of new prostheses allows you to form the correct bite height. Also, at the same time, it is necessary to visit other specialists of a narrow profile - a neurologist, endocrinologist, psychotherapist, etc.[1.2.4]

The main tactic of treatment is to influence the links of the pain symptom. So, the doctor may prescribe bromine, iron, tranquilizers, sedatives. B vitamins, lingual nerve blocks may be recommended to help restore its normal function. With dry mucous membranes and insufficient salivation, the doctor will prescribe a vitamin A solution or another agent to moisturize and stimulate saliva production.

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